

Technical and Tactical Training Methods of Basketball Players of 9-10 Classes in Schools

Muhammed Marsbek Uli Reypnazarov

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyoz, independent researcher

Abstract: This article talks about ways to involve young people in sports and further develop their technical and tactical skills.

Keywords: modes of action, stages of development, problem solution, technical and tactical solutions.

In sports schools, 31.7% of all pupils are in the preparatory groups, 65% in the training groups and 3.3% in the sports teams. Children aged 9-10 years in the preparatory group, 12-16 years in the training group, 16-20 years in the sports group. The basic principles of the shoe washing system are the universal shoe washing system for preparing children for bathing. In educational groups, these principles are emphasized, while special game elements are added. In special sports teams, the main principles are special preparations, which lead to the deepening of the special game, taking into account individual differences. The most important part of the technical training of young athletes is to learn technical movements such as stopping, turning, catching the ball, catching, carrying and driving.

Training of trained personnel in the use of various types of equipment (walking, jumping, jumping). and Tactical readiness exercises are considered to be related to tactical thinking and actions, and to the techniques learned to achieve individual actions, due to the ability of the participants to think and act. The technical rules of the game of basketball are qualified by combining the top teams of the league in both defense and defense in the team of the manager. The technique of the game of basketball is divided into two main parts:

- 1) technique of rhythm building.
- 2) Deference equipment.

Machine tools are divided into two groups: - machine tools. - ball milling equipment. Movement technique: Basketball player's stand - accommodates all the players in the same position. The legs are placed one foot in front of the other between the shoulder blades and the dizzers are less bent. In case of equal body weight, the hands are positioned next to the thoracic vertebrae, slightly bent to the hand, which allows the player to quickly move to the desired direction of the movement movement to love the field and other players, and to successfully perform actions. The main functions of the ball handling equipment are to run the ball, deliver the ball, transport the ball and drive the ball. Successful athlete in mastering the technique of basketball player.

The group can fly in the air, when the team wants to catch the ball, the ball must be caught by hand beforehand, so the basketball player kneels and touches the ball with his hands extended forward. And the skirt was between the fingers, and the thumb toward the front, and the great toe

toward the front. Such a position of the pitch makes it convenient to remove the ball. The multitude shall be taken with the fingers, and the rings shall be bowed, and the multitude shall be pulled before the breastplate. At this time, the legs are bent and the basketball player returns to the stand position. If there are signs that the predetermined group will be placed after the flight, then the group can be removed to a more favorable position without stopping in front of the chest.

Tactics is the theoretical and experimental part of the game process that teaches the organization of the game, the rational use of tools and equipment, and the forms that are used during the sport, and how to use them to clearly defeat the opponent. Current basketball tactics are based on a large arsenal of tools and forms of gameplay. The best use of them, and how they affect the course of the game, is determined by the facts of the game. These factors affect the ability of a team to compete against the opposing team (the team's formation, the level of players' enthusiasm, their morale, their technical and tactical skills) and to compete in the outdoor conditions (public opinion, lighting, the condition of the surface of the pitch, the difference in the size of the crowd, the presence of spectators).

Without the tools to play the game, without knowing the technique, the game process is impossible. However, if the structure of the technical preparation movements is not adapted to the training of other players, the tactical preparation of the player, or the team, is supplemented by the necessary equipment in the special conditions of the sport. Takes the first place in the tactical preparation, learns the combinations of games of different qualities. Combinations can be defined as mutually agreed actions that are practiced in the presence of all players of the team, within a clear system that is designed to create a favorable environment for the basketball player to make a basket. Combinations other than ten are the designed interactions of the players, which are embedded in the player's racing experience may have been executed. It is not just a question of passing a trained combination, but of its logical interpretation, prediction and adaptation to the actual race conditions. Basically, the time zone is divided into 3 according to the system of action.

1. One-time player.
2. Double decimals.
3. Triple decimals.

A group is a group of commands that belong to a group. In the course of the game, the team's defensive function is actively supported by the team's actions, the team takes the initiative in the game and forces the opponent to adopt a tactical project that is unfavorable to him. The head coach of the team must hit the ball into the opponent's basket, close the ball to the opponent's goal within 30 seconds of the winning shot, create favorable conditions for the completion of the basket, pass the ball vertically and then jump to the goal. This weapon must be used in well-planned tactical ways. Gathering tactics give the team the opportunity to use the most favorable conditions of the race, both in relation to the obvious opponent, and in the form of designed maneuvers. Depending on the mineral, it is possible to carry out all the activities of the settlement in an individual smooth settlement.

Depending on the classification of tactics, actions are divided into group and command. Each basketball player, who has made the most gains in the group, must take into account the individual tactical goals of the game against the opponent. In the rules of the game, when the ball is in a favorable position to hit the ball, it must be delivered to the opponent, and the ball must be sent to the opponent's basket. Only a high level of tactical readiness allows him to win in a defensive and individual game.

The action of the player without the ball includes the following: the defender escapes from the danger and receives the ball from his partner in the free space; the player receives the action from his partner in the free space; the player receives the action from his partner in the free

b) Expand the technical arsenals of new technology in the management of the process and ensure the implementation of a number of functions that are technically compatible with the individual characteristics of the workforce - learn to make different types of moves, taking into account how the opponent feels before the match, - extend their ability to work in a synchronized position, - improve their experience of the game in competitions of different scales, - increase the effectiveness of technical and tactical moves, - exceed the requirements set by a qualified team, 12-15 people in teams. In the lessons, the following arsenals of tools are used, mainly in the minority groups, in the form of drill bits, in the form of drill bits, in the form of flows, and in the form of individual arsenals, which are expanded with a variety of forms. The demonstration method differs from the talking method in that the exercises are performed in a standing position, and the play method is widely used in exercises on both the treadmills and the instruments that analyze the erosion and density of the skin. In the training classes, two types of loads are used: long-term washing with a certain activity (90-120 min) and short-term washing with a maximum intensity with a rest interval. Game preparation takes up a lot of space in this environment. Athletic training includes special physical exercises. The speed, agility, and balance of the washing machine are greatly enhanced, and the precision of the power is greatly improved. Exercises aimed at strengthening the muscles have little effect on the flexibility of the muscles and the body. In the worst case, never go to the bathroom. It is necessary to change the methodology of passing such glasses to the strength method.

At this stage, space will be given to accelerated exercises. Shooting exercises should be of a specific nature, closely related to the nature of the game, they should be located in a certain proportion, at a certain moment of the movement situation. Technical readiness is divided according to the accuracy of the speed technique. There are different types of glasses used to facilitate the technique. - the occurrence of a large number of actions if their complexes are the same and in that case the motor structure is not yet ready, - the occurrence of actions if their complexes are different, in a predetermined time interval, - this is also a different situation, - in situations of increasing contradiction, there is more than one clear solution, - in a functional or psychological situation, the actions take place spontaneously.

Targets of tactical readiness. - develops the ability to make quick tactical interactions in small groups and in teams; - develops the ability to use a selected system of thought and its variants when necessary; - develops the initiative in using the process of a tactical plan. In these groups, the training of players plays an important role. This is where teams of skilled players learn to play the game, solving individual puzzles in conjunction with other puzzles. It is considered to be the most accurate individual tactical preparation. In the annual cycle of sportsmen's training materials on the types of training are distributed as follows. The number of alarm clocks is increased, the number of tactical and integral preparations is increased.

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